

I-CLAIM

Improving the Living
and Labour Conditions
of Irregularised Migrant
Households in Europe

Public understanding and attitudes to irregular migration in the UK

Country report

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Executive Summary

This report presents findings from the I-CLAIM public perceptions survey on irregular migration, conducted in the United Kingdom in February 2025 with a nationally representative sample of 1,147 adults. The survey provides new evidence on what the UK public knows about irregular migration, how they define it, and their attitudes toward irregular migrants, particularly in the context of work.

The results reveal major gaps in knowledge. Most respondents significantly overestimated the number of irregular migrants within the UK's foreign-born population. While estimates suggest that irregular migrants account for around 10–13% of the foreign-born, over half of respondents placed the figure far higher. This pattern was particularly strong among older and right-leaning respondents, while younger adults and Labour or Liberal Democrats voters were more likely to underestimate the share.

When asked how irregular status arises, respondents strongly associated irregularity with unauthorised border crossings and pending asylum claims, reflecting dominant political and media narratives. Fewer recognised routine or administrative pathways to irregularity, such as overstaying a visa or losing lawful residence after changes in employment—processes that research shows are central to the production of irregular status in the UK.

Attitudes toward irregular migrants as workers were mixed. Respondents identified food delivery, construction, hospitality, cleaning, and care as the main sectors of irregular employment. In hiring experiments, they expressed pragmatic preferences: favouring candidates with longer UK residence, good recommendations, and family ties in the country, even if irregular. However, preferences were shaped by racialised hierarchies, with candidates from Nigeria and Bangladesh less favoured than those from Moldova.

Perceptions of integration hinged on English fluency and having family and friends in the UK. Social distance was lowest in public or commercial encounters and highest in private spaces such as the home.

Overall, the survey shows that UK perceptions of irregular migration are partial, uneven, and often distorted. Attitudes combine suspicion with pragmatism and show openness to social markers of belonging. These findings highlight the importance of addressing both misperceptions and the wider narrative environment that shapes public debates on irregularity.

1. Introduction

Information about public knowledge and attitudes toward irregular migration and irregular migrants, a situation where foreign nationals residing in a given country do not hold legal residence due to different circumstances, is limited. In order to improve our understanding of this issue, this report summarises the main findings from an online survey on public perceptions of irregular migration conducted among the public of the United Kingdom in February 2025. The survey is part of the programme of work of the Horizon Europe-funded project “Improving the living and labour conditions of irregularised migrant households in Europe” (I-CLAIM) project. The survey aims to explore public perceptions on the topic, especially given the lack of evidence on views toward irregular migration – and irregular migrants – in general, but especially within the context of work.

This report complements earlier work (Piemontese 2025) we carried out investigating the narrative construction of migrant irregularity in the United Kingdom across three primary domains: media, politics, and civil society in which we examined how different stakeholders frame and influence public discourse on irregular migration, with particular attention to the intersection of employment, gender, race, and family-related representations.

Overall, the study of public narratives showed how they are constructed and contested across media, politics, and civil society. It also pointed to the fundamental disjuncture between public narratives which single-mindedly focused on irregular crossings and borders and the reality of a phenomenon which has multiple footings and drivers and is shaped by the UK’s immigration policy and governance, what we have termed the legal and policy infrastructures of irregularity (Piemontese and Sigona 2024).

Informed by these research findings and the concept of ‘irregularity assemblage’ (Sigona and van Liempt 2025; Gonzales et al., 2019) which emphasises how irregularity is not a fixed status but rather a dynamic position vis-à-vis the state co-constructed at the intersection of different regulatory frameworks that encompasses not only migrants without a residence permit, but migrants increasingly at risk of irregularisation due to structural features of the immigration system, the I-CLAIM survey has investigated who counts for the UK public as an irregular migrant, what value they attach to this label and what are the consequences on how they respond to them.

The I-CLAIM survey aimed to contribute to the developing evidence based on irregular migration and irregular migrants through ‘traditional’ questions as well as survey experiments, an increasingly popular tool to gauge public attitudes (Sobolewska & Lessard-Phillips 2024). In this report, we use the findings from the survey to explore two main questions:

- 1) What does the public know about irregular migration and irregular migrants?
- 2) What are public attitudes toward irregular migration and irregular migrants within the context of work?

Before we present this, however, we provide background information about the survey and sample.

2. About the Survey

2.1. Development and methodology

The aim of the I-CLAIM survey was to gauge perceptions of, and attitudes toward, irregularity among the general UK public. This was done through an online survey, administered by YouGov, where more ‘traditional’ survey questions, as well as survey experiments,¹ were asked to UK respondents to fulfil the aim of grasping public opinion toward irregular migration and irregular migrants, but also gauge views toward immigration and collect relevant socio-demographic information.

The content of the survey was developed in collaboration with the I-CLAIM consortium through survey development workshops and discussions. It included 6 main sections and 25 questions (see Appendix for a summary table of the questions included in the survey). The survey was tested and piloted with a number of respondents prior to the fieldwork stage. The final dataset also included demographic information previously collected by YouGov as part of their panels².

2.2. Target population, sample and fieldwork

The target population for the survey was the UK adult population, with the aim to collect responses from at least 1,000 respondents (the sample). Participants in the survey were randomly drawn from YouGov’s panel of registered users, using “targeted quota sampling”. The sample aimed to reflect the makeup of the UK population and YouGov considered the following criteria when constructing the sample and producing sampling weights to ensure representativeness of the general population: age; gender and education level; vote at the 2024 General Election and region; social grade; EU Referendum vote; and level of political interest.

Responses from selected respondents were collected during the fieldwork stage, which occurred between 3rd and 14th February 2025. Responses were collected from a total of 1,147 respondents.

2.3. Data Analysis

The statistical software Stata was used for all analyses. The data was analysed through various means, using the most relevant types of analysis for the questions under investigation, using the provided sampling weights. In the case of categorical variables, percentage frequency distributions were used for univariate and bivariate statistics, and chi-squared tests helped determine the possible presence of a relationship in bivariate relationships. None of the percentages presented are based on fewer than 5 respondents. For continuous variables, means and standard deviations were derived, using t-tests and ANOVA (when relevant) to examine mean differences across groups. Data from the experiments used Average Marginal Components Effect (AMCE) (Hainmueller et al., 2014) to look at probability of selection across attribute categories and Marginal Means (MMs) (Leeper et al., 2020) to look at group-based preferences and

¹ Survey experiments are a way to gauge public opinion by experimentally changing question conditions/characteristics in order to look at effects of specific aspects (such as wording, characteristics, etc.) on responses. It has been increasingly used in migration studies (Sobolewska and Lessard-Phillips, 2024).

² See Abraham (2025) for a description of YouGov’s methodology.

likelihood of selection. Unless directly relevant, any respondent with missing information was not included in the provided statistics, leading to a variable sample size across the questions examined.

2.4. Survey respondents' main characteristics

Here we give a brief overview of the main characteristics of the I-CLAIM survey respondents for the United Kingdom; all related supporting tables can be found in the appendix (Tables A.2-A.3). The main respondent demographics (Table A.2) were as follows. The mean age of the sample was 48.6 years, with 48.2% of respondents aged 50 and over. There were 51.5% female respondents and 48.5% male respondents. Just over 14% of respondents reported as being a member of a minority ethnic group. The majority of respondents were either married or partnered, and mostly lived in urban areas. The geographical distribution of respondents was spread across the UK, with more respondents residing in the South East, London, the North West, and the East of England.

Moving onto more socio-demographic characteristics (Table A.3), 27.2% of the British respondents reported having low levels of education (up to GCSE or equivalent), 37.6% having medium levels of education (A-level or equivalent, up to university diploma), and 35.2% having high levels of education (first degree or higher). Just over 57% of respondents were in work (either full-time or part-time), and 40.8% reported a low household income (up to £29,999 per year), 22% a medium household income (£30,000-£44,999), and 37.2% a high level of household income (£45,000 and above). The majority of respondents (57%) reported a high social grade (middle class). Among those who voted, most respondents reported having voted for Labour (33.8%), followed by the Conservative Party (23.7%), Reform (14.3%), Liberal Democrats (12.3%), and Greens (7.6%). The reporting of the Brexit vote was spread across Remain and Leave, for those who had partaken in the referendum.

Given the survey's topic matter, we also explore the respondents' own links to, and experiences with, migration (Table A.4). Within the survey, this has been measured as being born outside of the UK (9.6% of respondents); having at least one parent born outside of the UK (23.8% of respondents), having some experience of living abroad (19% of respondents), and having immigrant friends (41.3% of respondents).

The characteristics shown above are useful for two reasons: they help us gauge the makeup of the survey respondents, and also provide us with main groups whose views we want to compare when it comes to knowledge and attitudes toward irregular migration and irregular migrants. For the purpose of this report, we will focus on differences across gender (male/female), age groups (18-39; 40-64; 65+), and political views through the party voted for at the last General Election (Labour, Conservative, Liberal Democrats, Reform UK, Other parties, No vote).

2.4.1. Views toward immigration

Other respondents' characteristics that we incorporate here include overall views toward immigrants and immigration. We include these as we deemed them important in shaping perceptions toward irregular migration and irregular migrants, as they are in shaping views related to migration (Richards et al 2025).

We started the survey by asking respondents about the main areas of (policy) concerns for their country as well as themselves, to gauge the prevalence of immigration as an issue. With regard to the perceptions of the relevance of immigration as a concern, 44.2% of respondents indicated that immigration was a top issue

for the UK, and 33.7% indicated that it an issue of relevance for themselves. While not a perceived area of concern by all respondents, a relatively large share of respondents did include it, and appears to match levels of concerns found elsewhere in more recent polling (Ipsos, 2025).

We also asked respondents about the perceived costs and benefits of migration with regard to (1) whether immigrants take out more than they put in in terms of taxes and services (Figure 1) and (2) whether the country's cultural life was undermined or enriched by immigrants (Figure 2). These questions emulated those asked in the European Social Survey (Heath et al., 2016), and respondents provided their answers on a scale from 0 (more negative outlook) to 10 (more positive outlook). For the purpose of this report, we grouped answers along 5 categories: Negative outlook (scores of 0-4); Neutral outlook (score 5); and Positive outlook (scores 6-10). We also explored differences in views across the main respondent groupings (gender, age and political affiliation).

As seen in Figure 1, just over 40% of respondents indicated that immigrants take out more than they put in regarding paying taxes and accessing services (negative outlook), whereas 43.5% indicated that immigrants put in more than they take out (positive outlook). Views toward the issue are generally consistent between men and women, whereas there are more differences across age groups (with older age groups holding a more negative outlook) and political affiliation (with those affiliating with Reform UK and the Conservative Party having a more negative outlook).

Figure 1 Perceived costs and benefits of migration among I-CLAIM survey respondents: immigrant take out/put in more (taxes and services). Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). Baseline N=1,067.

With regard to views toward whether the UK's culture was undermined or enriched by immigrants, 40.1% of respondents had a more negative outlook, whereas 49.3% had a more positive outlook. Women and

younger respondents appeared to have a more positive outlook. Again, respondents who voted for Reform UK exhibited a more negative outlook, as did respondents who voted for the Conservative Party.

Figure 2 Perceived costs and benefits of migration among I-CLAIM survey respondents: Cultural life undermined/enriched by immigrants. Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). Baseline N=1,098.

The picture above gives us a good indication as to the respondents that were included in the survey, their main characteristics, as well as their opinions toward immigration and immigrants in general. In the next section, we turn to their views toward irregular migration and irregular migrants.

3. Main Results

Now that we have a better understanding of who the survey respondents were, this section focuses on showcasing answers to the focal questions that this report aims to explore, namely:

- 1) What does the public know about irregular migration and irregular migrants? [knowledge section]
- 2) What are public attitudes toward irregular migration and irregular migrants within the context of work? [attitudes section]

Each question will be addressed in their dedicated section, first by showcasing answers for the whole sample, and then by investigating main group (gender, age, party voted for) differences.

3.1. Knowledge of irregular migration and irregular migrants

This section covers questions that were asked about respondents' knowledge about irregular migration and irregular migrants. We first look at knowledge about: the scale of, and the level of concern about, irregular migration; and scenarios leading to irregularity. We then move to more work-related topics, covering the sectors in which irregular migrants are deemed to work; perceived and social distance toward working irregular migrants.

3.1.1. *Scale and level of concern*

One big gap in knowledge is that of the scale of irregular migration in the UK. In order to look at this issue, we asked respondents to estimate the share of irregular migrants among all foreign-born people in the UK. Recent estimates have put the number of irregular migrants at between 10.5% and 13.1% of the foreign-born population (MIRREM, 2025). Based on the answers and the published estimates, we evaluated whether respondents' estimates about the share of irregular migrants in the UK were 'below the estimated range'; 'on/around the estimated range'; 'up to 10% above the estimated range'; and '10% above the estimated range'. Results are shown in Figure 3.

Results shown in the figure indicate that more than half of respondents overestimated the share of irregular migrants by over 10%, 14.8% were within 10% of the upper estimate, 10.1% were within the estimated range, and 18.3% underestimated the share of irregular migrants in the UK. There was variation in the response patterns between men and women (with men underestimating the share of irregular migrants, and overestimating by over 10%, more often than women), between age groups (with larger shares of older adults (65+) overestimating the share of irregular migrants), and across political affiliation (with Conservative and Reform UK voters as well as non-voters having larger shares of overestimation, and Labour, Liberal Democrats, and other party voters having larger shares of underestimation of irregular migrants).

Figure 3 Perception of the scale of irregular migration in the UK against estimates. Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). Baseline N=917

Respondents were also asked to gauge the extent to which irregular migration was a concern for the UK, using a 0 (not a concern) to 10 (a great concern) scale. Figure 4 presents the share of respondents who indicated that irregular migration was a larger concern (e.g., a score over 5 on the scale). Overall, 69.4% of respondents indicated that irregular migration was a concern for the UK. Larger shares of older respondents and respondents who voted Conservative or Reform UK indicated that irregular migration was a concern for the UK.

Figure 4 Irregular Migration as concern for the UK. Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). Baseline N=1,064.

3.1.2. *Becoming 'irregular': testing scenarios*

Besides questions related to the size of the population of irregular migrants and the relevance for policy, we set to find out more on what the public knows about how a person becomes an irregular migrant. One such question focused on presenting different types of scenarios potentially leading to irregularity, and see how often respondents would link those scenarios to irregularity.

The proposed scenarios were drawn from our earlier work, respectively, on the legal and policy infrastructures of irregularity (Piemontese and Sigona 2024) and the political and media narratives on irregularity in the UK (Piemontese 2025) which points to a misalignment between how a migrant can become irregularised in the UK, what we term the infrastructures of irregularity, and how the process is described in media and political narratives. The scenarios proposed included: (1) someone with an expired student visa; (2) someone crossing a border without documentation; (3) someone waiting to hear back from their asylum claim; (4) someone born in the UK to parents with legal residence; (5) someone hired through a recruitment company; (6) someone from the EU in-between contracts. Looking at public perceptions on these scenarios is particularly relevant given I-CLAIM's work on narrative of irregularisation (Piemontese 2025), which suggest that, despite the multiple drivers of irregularity, the political and media narrative not only overwhelming focus on unauthorised border crossings and boat migrants when talking about irregular migrants, but it also tend to criminalise asylum seekers portraying them under a negative light.

Table 1 presents the responses to the evaluation of the different scenarios and their linkage to irregularity. For each scenario, we show the share of respondents who answered that scenarios would likely lead to irregularity (e.g., choosing the ‘most of the time’ or ‘all of the time’ options), would be unlikely lead to irregularity (e.g., choosing the ‘never’ or ‘sometimes’ answer choices). We also show, for each scenario, the share of respondents who did not know whether the given scenario would lead to irregularity.

Table 1 Scenarios of irregularity

		Likelihood of scenario leading to irregularity		Uncertainty regarding scenario (N=1,147)
		Most/All of the time	Never/Sometimes	
Scenarios	Waiting to hear about their asylum claim (N=988)	64.3%	35.7%	15.10%
	Crossing a border without proper documentation (N=1,001)	55.7%	44.3%	13.9%
	Having an expired student visa (N=963)	33.1%	66.9%	16.6%
	Being born in the UK to parents who do not have legal residence status (N=930)	29.9%	70.1%	19.80%
	Being hired through a recruitment company (N=876)	29.8%	70.2%	23.30%
	Being a worker from the EU in the UK (N=813)	25.5%	74.5%	29.90%

Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025).

Among the scenarios, waiting on an asylum claim and crossing a border without documentation were the most often chosen scenarios as leading to irregularity, echoing the findings from the media and political narratives. This is especially noteworthy because asylum seekers waiting for a decision on their application have the right to stay in the UK. Moreover, as explicitly stated in the UN Refugee Convention, irregular border crossing should not preclude or negatively impact on the assessment of a person seeking international protection.

Looking at the results more closely, in terms of differences among respondents, we can see that there was agreement across all groupings regarding this aspect.

Figure 5 Evaluation of the scenarios leading to irregularity: waiting to hear about an asylum claim. Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025).

When it comes to irregular border crossings, older respondents tended to identify this scenario as more likely than younger respondents. There is a clear distinction along political affiliations, with over 68% of Conservative and 76% Reform voters expressing firm convictions on irregular border crossings leading to irregular status and only few undecided, while among Labour voters only 45% of respondents see this as a pathway to irregularity. Non-voters also had a relatively large share (59.5%) of respondents indicating this scenario as likely.

Figure 6 Evaluation of the scenarios leading to irregularity: crossing a border without documentation. Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025).

Among the scenarios chosen as least likely to lead to irregularity there are being the child of irregular migrants and being a worker from the EU. Both are scenarios we have encountered in our previous (Sigona and Hughes 2012) and current work with migrants without papers (Sigona et al 2025a; 2025b). The response to the scenario on children of irregular migrant parents echoes the ‘invisibility by design’ that Humphris and Sigona found when analysing the policy and political representation of these children (2019: 13):

“Undocumented migrant children are mostly absent from official policy and public discourse that relate to child protection and safeguarding in Europe. These children are not explicitly considered as undeserving, instead they are made institutionally invisible—as if they are not there. This invisibility is not an accident, it is by design and it is particularly striking in the case of the UK-born children of undocumented migrant parents. By law, these children not only inherit the legal status as undocumented, but also their status as migrants, despite the fact they may have never left the UK in their life.”

As shown in Figure 7, the invisibility of children of undocumented migrants is shared among all age and gender groups, However, political affiliation see an alignment between Conservative and Reform voters on the one hand, with over 60% of respondents seeing this scenario as unlikely, and Labour, and Liberal Democrats voters, on the other, with over 75% of respondents seeing the scenario as unlikely.

Figure 7 Evaluation of the scenarios leading to irregularity: children born to parents without legal residence. Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025).

As shown in the figure below (Figure 8) regarding the scenario concerning EU migrant workers, there is a general agreement among respondents, including Reform voters, that EU migrant workers are unlikely to find themselves irregular, interestingly, this is not the case. In fact, Benson and Sigona (2024: 2056) have shown that:

“EU nationals made up almost 50 per cent of those forcefully removed by the United Kingdom in 2022. In 2013, they constituted just over 10 per cent of all of those removed. These figures signal the increased visibility of EU migrants to the immigration control and enforcement apparatus”

Figure 8 Evaluation of the scenarios leading to irregularity: EU workers in the UK. Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025).

3.2. Irregular migrant and work: sectors & overall feelings

Given I-CLAIM’s focus on working conditions, knowledge of irregular migration within the context of work/employment was also gauged by asking respondents about the main sectors of work in which irregular migrants are represented and their feelings toward encountering working irregular migrants in their lives.

Despite over 60% of respondents linking work/employment to legal residence, respondents still identified the main sectors in which irregular migrants are deemed to work. Most often mentioned sectors included food delivery, construction, catering and hospitality, and agriculture for male irregular migrants; and cleaning, catering and hospitality, child and elderly care, and healthcare for female irregular migrants. These choices were generally consistent across all groups.

Table 2 Main sectors in which irregular migrants are deemed to work. Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025).

	First	Second	Third	Fourth
Male	Food delivery	Construction	Catering and hospitality	Agriculture
Female	Cleaning	Catering and hospitality	Child and elderly care	Healthcare

Respondents were also given the opportunity to write-in sectors not available in the provided list. Despite a small number of respondents choosing this option, an investigation of the free-text entry show that respondents also identified other sectors of relevance, such as the car wash industry, personal care services, as well as sex work, especially for female sectors.

We also asked respondents to express their level of ease toward irregular migrants in different professional settings (e.g., the assessed level of perceived ‘social distance’ between respondents and irregular migrants).

In other words, respondents were asked whether they would mind having an irregular migrant working in their home, their workplace, and a shop. Respondents were asked to record their level of ease in having irregular migrants in these settings on a scale from 0 (would not mind at all) to 10 (would mind a great deal). The mean levels of social distance for the overall sample and by group is shown in Figure 9, with higher scores indicating higher levels of social distance.

Figure 9 Social distance indicators. Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). Baseline Ns=1,043/1,008/1,059.

Results indicate that respondents have higher levels of social distance toward irregular migrants working in their home, a space within their private lives, and lower levels of social distance for encountering irregular migrants in their professional lives and in a shop setting. Encountering (whether knowingly or not) an irregular migrant in a shop had the lowest mean level of social distance across all groups, but we can also see variation in the perceived levels of social distance across groups. While levels of social distance are lower for irregular migrants encountered in the workplace, in some instances (men, younger respondents, Labour and Liberal Democrats, Reform and other voters) the levels are not much different than for irregular migrants encountered in a home setting. Lower mean levels of social distance are also found for women (workplace and shops), younger adults, as well as respondents who voted for Labour, Liberal Democrats, and other parties at the 2024 General Election.

The focus on work sectors and the ease that respondents have regarding the (hypothetical) presence of irregular migrants in various settings is especially relevant to understand overall attitudes towards working irregular migrant, to which we now turn.

3.3. Attitudes

Now that we have explored the respondents' knowledge of irregular migration and feelings of social distance toward irregular migrants in different settings, we delve into more specific attitudes toward irregular migration within the context of work/employment, looking also at the intersection with racialisation and gender. This is especially relevant within the context of I-CLAIM, where public perceptions and attitudes are relevant to understandings of the narrative construction, and production, of irregularity. Within the survey, we examined these through different means, some of which we have covered above, but also by including the use of survey experiments, a generally unobtrusive way to tease out individual preferences in instances where we are dealing with sensitive topics, as is the case here, with as little bias as possible.

In this section, we present results from two of the survey's experiments, one that focuses on hiring preference for irregular migrants, and another showing evaluations of irregular migrants' level of integration in UK society.

3.3.1. *Hiring choice*

In the experiment looking at hiring preferences, respondents were presented with hypothetical applicants to hire to care for a relative. This is especially relevant given the importance of the care sector identified by respondents as a main sector of work for irregular migrants. Respondents were presented with two pairs of applicants, one male and one female, to hire for the job, with certain sets of characteristics, but who were unable to provide proof of residence in the UK, a feature of irregular status. Based on the information presented, respondents had to indicate the likelihood of hiring either candidate, but also choose who to hire between both candidates. Aspects that varied included country of origin and associate name (see Appendix); length of residence in the UK; recommendation status; and location of family. Figure 10 shows an example of what was presented to respondents.

Figure 11 Results from hiring choice experiment (AMCEs). Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=1,147.

Results from Figure 11 indicate that, when hiring, respondents were less likely to hire candidates from Bangladesh and Nigeria than from Moldova. This was consistent for both male and female applicants, even if in the case of female applicants, the negative likelihood of hiring a candidate from Bangladesh was not as strong. Respondents were more likely to hire candidates with a longer stay of residence and who came recommended by a friend. Finally, candidates who were providing for their family based in the UK were more positively evaluated for hiring, especially for female candidates.

It is also possible to show the overall popularity of specific attributes across groups of respondents. This is done through the use of Marginal Means, which indicates how each individual attributes are favoured by respondents, and shown in Figures 12-14. A data point to the right of the dotted line indicates a positive preference, whereas one to the left indicates a negative preference.

What we can see from the Figure 12 is that, in their hiring choices, male respondents tended to more positively favour candidates from Moldova than female respondents, but also favour candidates from Nigeria negatively. Female respondents were slightly more positive or negative in their preference for length of residence and recommendation status compared to male respondents.

Figure 12 Attribute preference by gender of respondent, hiring choice experiment (Marginal Means). Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=1,147.

With regard to the age groups of respondents, most differences in the preferences operated at the level of the origin of respondents. This is especially the case for candidates from Moldova and Nigeria, where a generational gap appears to exist in the preference for these attributes (more positive for the older age group for Moldova, more negative for the candidate from Nigeria).

Figure 13 Attribute preference by age group of respondent, hiring choice experiment (Marginal Means). Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=1,147.

Finally, with regard to political affiliation, more polarised views were expressed by Conservative and Reform UK voters with regard to the origin of the candidates, with Conservative and Reform UK voters expressing a stronger preference for the Moldovan candidate, Reform UK voters expressing a stronger negative preference for the Bangladeshi candidate, and Conservative, Reform UK and Other voters expressing a stronger negative preference for the Nigerian candidate. Reform UK voters were not swayed by length of residence and recommendation status in their hiring choice (data points crossing the dotted line) and were more generally less influenced by the location of the family.

Figure 14 Attribute preference by party affiliation of respondent, hiring choice experiment (Marginal Means). Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=1,147.

3.3.2. Perceptions of integration and settlement

We also investigated respondents' attitudes toward irregular migrants within the context of work through the lens of their perceptions of long-term settlement, or integration, of irregular migrants engaging in work. This is especially relevant given that, despite popular discourses about irregularity focusing mostly on newly-arrived migrants, some irregular migrants have settled in the UK for a number of years. Moreover, exploring perceptions of male irregular migrants, who tend to be some of the most negatively portrayed within popular discourse, was deemed of relevance.

As part of this, respondents were asked to evaluate the level of integration of two profiles of male irregular migrants, one from Kosovo and one from Nigeria on a scale from 0 (not well integrated at all) to 10 (very well integrated). Each profile contained a set number of characteristics deemed to influence evaluations of the level of integration that were randomly varied for each profile (see Appendix for a detailed list of characteristics): reason for migration; language fluency; religiosity; location of family and friends; and marital status. Example of what was seen by respondents is shown in Figure 15.

Figure 16 Results from evaluation of integration experiment, all profiles (AMCEs). Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=1,080.

Figure 17 Results from evaluation of integration experiment, by origin of profile (AMCEs). Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=1,080.

If we, however, look at group differences in the preference for individual attributes, we can see that, overall, male respondents were generally more negative in their evaluation for integration than female respondents. This is exemplified by the fact that most attributes led to a more negative evaluation of integration (data points to the left of the dotted line). The preferences were also consistent regardless of the origin linked to the profile (not shown here).

Figure 18 Attribute preference by age group of respondents, evaluation of integration experiment (Marginal Means). Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=1,080.

When comparing across age groups, we see that the various attributes were linked to more negative preferences among older age groups. Respondents in the 40-64 age group did, however, express a positive preference for profiles showing language fluency. Respondents in the youngest age groups did have a positive preference for language fluency, the location of family and friends in the UK, and profiles of married individuals. The strongest negative preferences were for lack of language fluency and location of family and friendship in the country of origin for all age groups, to various extents. Note that these patterns held regardless of the origin of the profile.

Figure 19 Attribute preference by age group of respondents, evaluation of integration experiment (Marginal Means).
 Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=1,080.

Finally, with regard to differences across party affiliation, we see that Reform UK and Conservative voters were also more negative in their evaluations, whereas Labour and Liberal Democrat voters expressed some more neutral and positive preferences. Language fluency was linked to positive preferences for both Labour and Liberal Democrat voters, as was UK-based family for Labour voters. Reform UK voters were the most negative in their evaluation of integration, with all attributes linked to negative preferences. This reflects the picture shown above but does show that, overall, respondents favoured many of the attributes more negatively, but that the extent of negative evaluation varies depending on party affiliation.

Figure 20 Attribute preference by party affiliation of respondents, evaluation of integration experiment (Marginal Means).
 Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=1,080.

Results from this experiment do confirm that, even when it comes to irregular migrants, aspects linked to social integration are the ones that appear to matter the most (Sobolewska, Galandini and Lessard-Phillips, 2016).

4. Conclusion

This report has provided new insights into how the UK public understands and perceives irregular migration, with a particular focus on work and employment. The findings highlight a number of recurring themes: widespread gaps in knowledge, the persistence of partial or distorted narratives, the influence of political affiliation and age in shaping attitudes, and the coexistence of suspicion and pragmatism when considering the role of irregular migrants in UK society.

A first striking finding is the limited and uneven public knowledge about irregularity. Most respondents significantly overestimated the share of irregular migrants within the UK’s foreign-born population. Current estimates suggest that irregular migrants account for around 10–13% of the foreign-born, yet more than half of respondents placed the figure far higher. This tendency was particularly strong among older respondents and those who identified with Conservative and Reform UK parties. Conversely, younger adults and Labour or Liberal Democrat voters were more likely to underestimate the proportion. These patterns underscore how perceptions are often less about evidence and more about the interpretative frames made available by political discourse and media coverage.

Linked to this, there is a marked disconnect between the policy infrastructures of irregularity and public understandings of how irregular status arises. While respondents could readily identify scenarios such as unauthorised border crossing or waiting for an asylum decision as leading to irregularity, they were far less

certain when asked about more routine or bureaucratic routes to irregularisation, such as overstaying a visa or losing lawful residence due to employment changes. This reflects broader trends in the UK, where political and media narratives have narrowed irregularity to border spectacle and asylum, overshadowing the complex legal and policy processes that produce irregular status.

At the same time, the survey highlights ambivalent attitudes toward irregular migrants as workers. Respondents recognised irregular migrants as present in key sectors of the UK economy—particularly food delivery, construction, hospitality, cleaning, and care. In hiring experiments, they showed a degree of pragmatism, favouring candidates with longer residence in the UK, strong recommendations, and family ties in the country, even when aware of their irregular status. Yet, these preferences were also mediated by racialised and gendered hierarchies: candidates from Nigeria or Bangladesh were consistently less favoured than those from Moldova, with stronger negative responses among older and right-leaning respondents; and female candidates more harshly judged for having families in their countries of origin.

Perceptions of integration similarly revolved around markers of belonging, especially English fluency and the presence of family and friends in the UK. Respondents across political and demographic groups associated these characteristics with higher levels of integration, though Conservative and Reform UK voters remained more sceptical overall. Social distance measures reinforced this ambivalence: while many respondents reported little concern about encountering irregular migrants in public or commercial spaces, acceptance declined sharply when considering more intimate or private settings, such as the home.

Taken together, these findings suggest that public perceptions of irregular migration in the UK are deeply shaped by the irregularity assemblage: the interplay of political narratives, legal infrastructures, and social imaginaries that construct who counts as irregular and how they are valued. Public knowledge is partial, often inaccurate, and unevenly distributed across demographic and political lines. Yet attitudes are not uniformly negative: they are layered with pragmatism, shaped by proximity and sectoral needs, and open to markers of social integration.

For policy, these insights matter. Efforts to reduce hostility toward migrants cannot succeed if they focus solely on correcting misperceptions of scale; they must also address the wider narrative environment that narrows irregularity to borders and boats while obscuring the systemic production of irregular status through immigration rules. Moreover, given the role of work in shaping public perceptions, policy debates that acknowledge irregular migrants' economic and social contributions may find more traction with sections of the public than narratives built purely on humanitarian or security grounds.

Ultimately, the survey highlights that irregular migration is not only a legal condition but a social and political category, contested and refracted through the lenses of age, class, gender, race, and political identity. Understanding these dynamics is essential if we are to foster more informed, balanced, and constructive debates on irregularity in the UK.

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Appendices

Table A.1 Overview of the content of the I-CLAIM survey

Section	Description of question	
A. Overall concerns	Top issues facing the country today	
	Top issues facing you personally	
B. Attitudes and experience toward immigration	Close friends as immigrants (split allocation)	
	Whether immigrants take more in or out of society	
	Whether cultural like undermined or enriched by immigrants	
	Views on immigrants and work	
C. Perception of irregular migration/migrants	Percentage of irregular migrants in country	
	Whether irregular migration is a concern in country	
	Work sector for female irregular migrants	
	Work sector for male irregular migrants	
	Scenarios of irregularity	
D. Attitudes toward irregular migration and work/employment	List experiment on policy deservingness for female cleaner	
	Conjoint experiment – female care workers	
	Likelihood of hiring applicant 1	
	Likelihood of hiring applicant 2	
	Choice of applicant	
	Conjoint experiment – male care workers	
	Likelihood of hiring applicant 1	
	Likelihood of hiring applicant 2	
	Choice of applicant	
	Factorial experiments – Evaluation of integration for male irregular migrant 1 and for male irregular migrant 2	
	Social distance indicator – 3 scenarios	
	E. Further demographics	Immigrant generation
		Religiosity
Member of ethnic minority group		
Has lived outside of country for over 1 year		

Table A.2: Main Demographics

Main Respondent Demographics, UK	
Age (N=1,147)	48.6 (17.6)
Age group (N=1,147)	
18-29	16.9%
30-39	20.7%
40-49	14.2%
50-59	16.8%
60-69	17.3%
70+	14.1%
Gender (N=1,147)	
Male	48.5%
Female	51.5%
Ethnic minority (N=1,085)	
No	85.7%
Yes	14.3%
Marital Status (N=1,145)	
Married, partnership, living as married	54.4%
Separated/divorced/widowed	11.0%
Never married	34.7%
Region (N=1,147)	
North East	4.3%
North West	10.7%
Yorkshire and the Humber	8.0%
East Midlands	7.0%
West Midlands	8.9%
East of England	10.5%
London	11.5%
South East	13.2%
South West	9.6%
Wales	5.2%
Scotland	8.3%
Northern Ireland	2.8%
Urban/Rural (N=1,054)	
Urban	77.7%
Rural	22.3%

Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025).

Table A.3: Socio-demographics

Respondent Socio-Demographics, UK	
Education level (N=1,104)	
Low	27.2%
Medium	37.6%
High	35.2%
Work status (active/inactive) (N=1,147)	
Working (full time/ part time)	57.1%
Not working (student, pensioner, family carer, unemployed etc.)	42.9%
HH income (N=885)	
Low	40.8%
Medium	22.0%
High	37.2%
Social grade (N=1,147)	
ABC1	57.0%
C2DE	43.0%
Party voted for, 2024 (N=1,147)	
Conservatives	17.4%
Labour	24.8%
Liberal Democrats	9.0%
Reform UK	10.5%
Green	5.6%
Other	6.0%
DK or no vote	26.7%
Brexit vote (N=1,126)	
I voted to Remain	36.3%
I voted to Leave	36.5%
I did not vote	27.2%

Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025)

Table A.4: Respondents' Links to migration

Respondent Links to migration, UK	
Country of birth (N=1,134)	
Outside survey country	9.6%
In survey country	90.4%
Immigrant parentage (N=1,138)	
None	76.2%
One parent	7.8%
Two parents	16.0%
Experience of migration (N=1,135)	
No	81.0%
Yes	19.0%
Has immigrant friends (N=1,115)	
None	58.7%
Yes, several	14.5%
Yes, a few	26.8%

Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025)

Table A.5 Attributes for hiring experiment randomly selected for each profile.

COUNTRY OF ORIGIN: FEMALE NAME/MALE NAME Two of three chosen for the female and male candidates.	Moldova: Elena/Vasile Bangladesh: Asma/Abdul Nigeria: Ogechi/Chukwuma
LENGTH OF RESIDENCE One of two.	under a year 5 years
RECOMMENDATION STATUS One of two.	<no recommendation> but comes recommended by a friend
LOCATION OF FAMILY One of two.	Country of origin Survey country

Table A.6 Attributes for integration experiments randomly selected for each profile.

COUNTRY OF ORIGIN/NAME One for each profile	Kosovo: Klajdi Nigeria: Ayo
REASON FOR MIGRATION One of four.	<no reason stated> to improve his living standards to get an education to seek protection
SURVEY COUNTRY LANGUAGE FLUENCY One of two.	speaks does not speak
RELIGIOSITY One of two.	He regularly practices his religion. <none stated>
LOCATION OF FRIENDS One of two.	From COUNTRY OF ORIGIN From SURVEY COUNTRY
FAMILY STATUS One of two.	He is single He has a family
LOCATION OF FAMILY If has family One of two.	In COUNTRY OF ORIGIN In SURVEY COUNTRY

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I-CLAIM

Improving the Living
and Labour Conditions
of Irregularised Migrant
Households in Europe